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DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES: A COMPARISON BETWEEN NEUTRON AND X-RAY TOMOGRAPHY

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Tomography

- Tomography may refer to any imaging technique used to view sections of an object using a non-destructive penetrating wave.
- Tomography is typically used to create 3D scalar fields in which each voxel encodes for local attenuation rate of the wave.
- The utility of tomography for particular applications is limited by resolution, contrast (attenuation), magnification, acquisition time, artefacts, noise, etc.
- Two tomographic techniques will be compared in this paper, with a focus on the application to damage in carbon fibre textile composites:
 - Micro X-ray Computed Tomography (microCT, μ CT)
 - Neutron Tomography (NT)

Facilities

- University of New South Wales (UNSW)
Tyree μ CT Lab

- Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO) DINGO Neutron Tomography Beamline

Contrast

μ CT

- X-ray attenuation is close to monotonic with atomic number:
 - Light elements have minimal absorption
- Material density is a good indicator of attenuation
- Minimal contrast between carbon fibre and polymer resins
- Large contrast between composite and metallic inclusions can lead to artefacts

Monica Castellanos, Maria & Mcauley, Arnold & Curtis, Joseph. (2016). Investigating Structure and Dynamics of Proteins in Amorphous Phases Using Neutron Scattering. Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal

NT

- Thermal neutron cross-section is not monotonically linked to Z-number:
 - Hydrogen has very high relative absorption
- Hydrogen concentration is a good indicator of attenuation
- Significant contrast between fibre and resin
- Structural metals are typically lower or similar attenuation than polymers

Radioactive specimens or fixtures are possible, but can be managed in most cases.

Acquisition

- Conical beam – geometric magnification
- Direct x-ray detection elements – no detector magnification

- Collimated beam – no geometric magnification
- Optical detection of scintillation events – optical magnification

Resolution

μ CT

- Geometric magnification - resolution strongly link to specimen size
- Resolution $<1 \mu\text{m}$ can be achieved for very small specimens ($<1\text{-}2 \text{ mm}$)
- Practical limit for textile composites is $3\text{-}5 \mu\text{m}$

NT

- No geometric magnification
- Resolution typically bottlenecked by:
 - Thermal neutron scintillation efficiency
 - Noise (acquisition time)
- Typical resolution $10\text{-}15 \mu\text{m}$

Chowdhury, N. T., C. T., Pearce, G. M., Walsh, S. D. C., Latham, S. J., Middleton, J. P., & Beeching, L. (2019). Design of an uncontaminated textile CFRP specimen optimised for both mechanical testing and X-ray microtomography. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 123, 208-221.

Specimens

Tensile Coupon

- Failed tensile specimen:
 - T300/VTM264, twill, ± 45

Bolted Joint

- Combined bearing and pull-through loaded bolted joint:
 - Ti-6Al-4V Hi-lok fastener
 - IM7/977-3, 5 harness satin, quasi-isotropic

Note: Specimen images are representative. They are not the actual scanned specimens

Plane parallel to coupon orientation

Loading axis horizontal for: μ CT (left) and NT (centre)

Loading axis vertical for Full FoV NT (right). Contrast increased to highlight resin rich regions.

Tensile Specimen

Observations

- Damage detection and segmentation is possible for both μ CT and NT.
- Resolution is significantly higher for μ CT ($\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ vs $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$). Small specimen size favours μ CT in this case.
- Fibre orientation information is present in the μ CT data. Voxel size is below the nonlinear transition threshold, facilitating orientation-based segmentation of tows.
- NT has a much larger field of view (no geometric magnification). This level of resolution is possible for larger parts than scanned here, facilitating damage characterisation over much larger volumes than μ CT.
- NT brightest (i.e. highest attenuation) in the resin-rich regions.

μ CT (left) and NT (right)

Three orthogonal section planes through the specimen are shown (top, middle, bottom)

Joint Specimen

Observations

- Titanium fastener creates unavoidable artefacts in μ CT due to the large relative attenuation between the fastener and composite. Damage characterisation and segmentation is not possible in the vicinity of the bolt.
- NT avoids this class of artefact because the attenuation of composite is higher than the fastener, and the relative attenuation difference is smaller.
- NT is the far preferred choice for this specimen configuration.

NT reconstructions

Conclusions

- μ CT and NT offer complementary capabilities for investigating damage in carbon fibre textile composites.
- For composite specimens free from dense metallic inclusions, both μ CT and NT can resolve damage and provide data for further analysis.
- NT cannot yet achieve high enough resolution to directly capture fibre orientation information, so orientation-based segmentation is not possible.
- CT is the clear choice for small composite specimens.
- NT is the preferred option for large composite specimens or composite specimens with dense metallic components.

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- 7447 - *Examining Crack Propagation in Composites using a newly designed In-Situ Test Fixture*

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